

BANGLADESH UNIVERSITY OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY
(BUET)

DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

ME- 310

(HEAT TRANSFER EQUIPMENT DESIGN)

PROJECT TITLE

DESIGN OF A DOUBLE TUBE HEAT EXCHANGER

SUBMITTED BY

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Abstract

A heat exchanger is a device designed to efficiently transfer heat between two process fluids, are used in industrial and household processes. In this project, we developed a double-pipe heat exchanger with a multi-pass parallel flow configuration. The inner pipe is constructed from copper, while the outer pipe is made of mild steel. Both fluids used in the heat exchange process are water, and their flow rates are selected to ensure cost-effectiveness.

To assess the heat exchanger's performance and pressure drop, we employed the Log Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD) method. We utilized SolidWorks software for the project's design phase and HTRI software to determine the optimal design configuration. The necessary correlations for calculating the Nusselt number and other relevant data are taken from reference books.

1 Introduction

Double pipe heat exchangers are among the simplest heat exchange devices. They consist of two pipes, one placed concentrically within the other. The inner pipe carries one fluid, while the outer pipe carries another fluid, creating an annulus space between them. Heat transfer occurs through the solid wall of the inner pipe, preventing direct contact between the two fluids. The performance of this device depends on three key factors: the heat transfer area, the heat transfer coefficient, and the Log-mean temperature difference.

It is important to note that double pipe heat exchangers have a significant drawback: they offer limited heat transfer area when compared to shell-and-tube heat exchangers. Consequently, their applicability is constrained to specific situations. To increase the heat transfer area, the length of the inner tube must be extended. However, this comes at the expense of material costs and an increase in pressure drop.

In this project, we aimed to design a multi-pass (4-pass) parallel flow double pipe heat exchanger with specific performance requirements. Both the hot and cold fluids are chosen for this project are water due to its ready availability. All calculations are conducted using the Log Mean Temperature Difference (LMTD) method.

2 Problem statement

0.2 kg/s of water, coming from an industry is to be cooled from 95°C to 85 °C by means of cool water, available at 20 °C. The outlet temperature of the cool water should not be more than 28 °C to avoid thermal water pollution. Design a multi pass double pipe heat exchanger considering these criteria.

3 Objective

- To determine the overall heat transfer coefficient for the double pipe heat exchanger for parallel (or co-current) flow.
- To determine required heat transfer length for given criteria.
- To study the performance and characteristics of double pipe, water to water, concentric tube heat exchanger

- To study and evaluate the effects of flow conditions and flow configurations on the rate of heat transfer through thin-walled tube.
- To construct a prototype.

4 Flowchart

5 Designs

Schematic Design:

SolidWorks design:

6 Calculation

Known data:

Mass flow rate of hot water $m_h = 0.2 \text{ kg/s}$

Inlet temperature of hot water, $T_{hi} = 95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Inlet temperature of cold water, $T_{ci} = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Outlet temperature of hot water, $T_{ho} = 85 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Allowable outlet temperature of cold water, $T_{co} = 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Step 1: Pipe and Shell Selection:

Pipe Selection:

Economic velocity of water is 1.4 to 3 m/s

$$A_{\min} = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho v_{\min}} = \frac{0.1}{965.3 \times 1.4} = 0.000069 \text{ m}^2 \quad \blacktriangleright \quad ID_{P, \min} = 9.37 \text{ mm}$$

$$A_{\max} = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho v_{\max}} = \frac{0.1}{965.3 \times 3} = 0.0000147 \text{ m}^2 \quad \blacktriangleright \quad ID_{P, \max} = 13.726 \text{ mm}$$

Available pipe size in this range is 3/8 standard type M copper tubing.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{So, } ID_p &= 0.450 \text{ inch} = 11.43 \text{ mm OD}_p \\ &= 0.500 \text{ inch} = 12.7 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

and $V_a = 2.021 \text{ m/s}$

Shell selection:

Allowable temperature rise of cold water is 8°C From energy balance between hot and cold fluid,

$$Q_H = Q_c$$

$$\Rightarrow (m \cdot Cp)_H \cdot (T_{hi} - T_{co}) = (m \cdot Cp)_c \cdot (T_{ci} - T_{co})$$

$$\Rightarrow 0.2 \cdot (95 - 85) = m_c \cdot (28 - 20)$$

$$\Rightarrow m_c = 0.25 \text{ kg/s}$$

According to economic velocity of water, $v_{\max} = 3 \text{ m/s}$ and $v_{\min} = 1.4 \text{ m/s}$.

$$A_{\min} = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho v_{\min}} = \frac{0.25}{997.2 \times 1.4} = 0.0000835 \text{ m}^2 \quad \blacktriangleright \quad ID_{s, \min} = 16.36 \text{ mm}$$

$$A_{\max} = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho v_{\max}} = \frac{0.25}{997.2 \times 3} = 0.0000179 \text{ m}^2 \quad \blacktriangleright \quad ID_{P, \max} = 19.73 \text{ mm}$$

Available pipe size in this range is 3/4 standard type M copper tubing. So, $ID_s = 0.811 \text{ inch} = 20.5 \text{ mm}$

Corresponding $V_s = 1.213 \text{ m/s}$, close to economic velocity.

Step 2: Film coefficient determination:

For pipe:

Here,

$$\rho = \rho @ 90^\circ\text{C} = 965.3 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

$$V = 2.02193 \text{ m/s} \quad D = ID_p = 0.01143 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Reynolds number} = \frac{\rho v D}{\mu} = \frac{965.3 \times 2.02192 \times 0.01143}{3.15 \times 10^{-4}} = 70726 \quad (\text{turbulent flow})$$

$$Nu = \frac{h_i D_i}{K_i} = 0.023 \cdot (\text{Re})^{0.8} \cdot (\text{Pr})^{0.33} \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.14}$$

$$h_i = 12855.7 \quad \longrightarrow \quad h_{io} = 11570.13$$

For annulus:

Here,

$$\rho = \rho @ 24^{\circ}\text{C} = 997.2 \text{ kg/m}^3 V=1.21 \text{ m/s}$$

$$D=ID_p=0.0207 \text{ m}$$

$$\mu = 0.000910 \text{ Pa-s}$$

$$\text{Reynolds number} = \frac{\rho v D_e}{\mu} = \frac{997.2 \times 1.21 \times 0.0207}{0.000910} = 27523.6 \text{ (turbulent flow)}$$

$$Nu = \frac{h_i D_i}{K_i} = 0.023 * (\text{Re})^{0.8} * (\text{Pr})^{0.33} \left(\frac{\mu}{\mu_w} \right)^{0.14}$$

$$\Rightarrow h_o = 5804.86 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$$

For wall temperature, heat conduction flux formula can be applied.

$$h_i * (T_w - T_{c,\text{mean}}) = h_o * (T_{h,\text{mean}} - T_w)$$

$$\Rightarrow T_w = 68.58^{\circ} \text{ C}$$

After iteration two time,

$$h_{io} = 11384.078501 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$h_o = 5525 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$$

Step:3 Overall heat transfer coefficient

$$\text{Without fouling factor: } \frac{1}{U_o} = \frac{1}{h_i} + \frac{1}{h_o}$$

$$\Rightarrow U_o = 3.47 \times 10^3 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$$

$$\text{With fouling factor: } \frac{1}{U_o} = \frac{1}{h_i} + \frac{1}{h_o} + R_{f,i} + R_{f,o}$$

$$\Rightarrow U_o = 2 \times 10^3 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$$

Step 4: Length Calculation

From equation of energy balance,

$$U_o * A * \Delta T_{lm} = (\dot{m} * C_p)_c * (T_{c,i} - T_{c,o})$$

$$\text{Here, LMTD for parallel flow} = \frac{(T_{h,i} - T_{c,i}) - (T_{h,o} - T_{c,o})}{\ln \left(\frac{T_{h,i} - T_{c,o}}{T_{h,o} - T_{c,i}} \right)} = 65.99^{\circ} \text{ C}$$

$$\text{Without fouling, } L = 0.88 \text{ m}$$

With fouling, $L = 1.4$ m

Step5: Pressure Drop Calculation

Since the flow is turbulent in both tube and annular region,

$$\text{Friction coefficient} = (1.82 \log (Re) - 1.64) (Re)^{-1.64} - 2$$

In tube region, $f = 0.02$

In annular region, $f = 0.02725$

$$\text{So, pressure drop in tube region} = \frac{fL}{ID_p} * \frac{1}{2} * \rho v^2 = 550.5 \text{ Pa}$$

$$\text{So, pressure drop in annular region} = \frac{fL}{ID_p} * \frac{1}{2} * \rho v^2 = 4791 \text{ Pa}$$

Both are less than 70 Kpa

Final Data Considered for Project

Inner pipe inside diameter, $ID_p = 0.450$ inch = 11 mm

Inner pipe outside diameter, $OD_p = 0.5$ inch = 12.5 mm

Outer shell inside diameter, $ID_s = 21$ mm

Corresponding, tube side fluid velocity = 2.1802 m/s (within the economic velocity)
annular side fluid velocity = 1.121 m/s (close to the economic velocity)

Following the same procedure,

Length of the pipe, without fouling = 0.98 m

with fouling = 1.66 m

So, L = length of each pass = 0.41 m (inches, the project is designed considering fouling factor)

Pressure drops,

in tube region, without fouling = 377.7269 pa

With fouling = 2595.563 pa

In annular region, without fouling = 2595 Pa

with fouling = 3861.042 Pa

Software Calculations:

HTRI		Output Summary		Page 1	
Xhpe E Ver. 6.00		2/23/2022 12:46 SN: Vals100+		SI Units	
Released to the following HTRI Member Company: BUET Shuvo Chowdhury					
Rating - Horizontal Cocurrent Flow Hairpin With No Baffles See Data Check Messages Report for Informative Messages. See Runtime Message Report for Warning Messages.					
Process Conditions		Cold Shellside		Hot Tubeside	
Fluid name			Cold Water		Hot Water
Flow rate (kg/s)			0.2500		0.2000
Inlet/Outlet Y (Wt. frac vap.)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
Inlet/Outlet T (Deg C)	20.00		28.05	95.00	85.00
Inlet P/Avg (kPa)	0.000		0.000	0.000	0.000
dP/Allow. (kPa)	6.133		0.000	17.699	0.000
Fouling (m2-K/W)			0.000100		0.000111
Exchanger Performance					
Shell h (W/m2-K)	5343.93		Actual U (W/m2-K)		1960.50
Tube h (W/m2-K)	18177.0		Required U (W/m2-K)		1916.43
Hot regime (-)	Sens. Liquid		Duty (MegaWatts)		0.0084
Cold regime (-)	Sens. Liquid		Area (m2)		0.067
EMTD (Deg C)	65.6		Overdesign (%)		2.30
Shell Geometry			Baffle Geometry		
Type (-)	Hairpin		Baffle type (-)		None
Shell ID (mm)	20.789		Baffle cut (Pct Dia.)		
Series (-)	1		Baffle orientation (-)		
Parallel (-)	1		Central spacing (mm)		1702.80
Orientation (deg)	0.00		Crosspasses (-)		1
Tube Geometry			Nozzles		
Tube type (-)	Plain		Shell inlet (mm)		18.711
Tube OD (mm)	12.500		Shell outlet (mm)		18.711
Nominal length (m)	0.800		Inlet height (mm)		4.145
Pitch ratio (-)			Outlet height (mm)		4.145
Layout (deg)	30		Tube inlet (mm)		18.711
Tubecount (-)	1		Tube outlet (mm)		18.711
Thermal Resistance, %		Velocities, m/s		Flow Fractions	
Shell	36.69	Shellside	1.16	A	
Tube	14.19	Tubeside	2.92	B	1.000
Fouling	48.24	Crossflow	0.00	C	0.000
Metal	0.89	Window	1.16	E	
				F	

Overdesign = 2.3%

7 Experimental Result

1st Run:

Mass Flow Rate of hot Water= 0.046 kg/s Inlet

temperature of Hot Water =87°C Outlet

temperature of Hot Water= 62°C Mass Flow rate

of cold water=0.051 kg/s Inlet Temperature of

cold water=26.5°C Outlet Temperature of cold

Water=40°C

Temp Fall=15 °C

Temp Rise=13.5 °C

2nd Part:

Mass Flow Rate of hot Water =0.046kg/s

Tem Fall =19.5 °C

Inlet temperature of Hot Water =89.5°C Outlet
temperature of Hot Water= 70°C Mass Flow rate
of cold water=0.051 kg/s Inlet Temperature of
cold water=27°C Outlet Temperature of cold
Water=42°C

Tem Rise =15 °C

8 Conclusions

Despite of that, the double pipe heat exchanger is the simplest form the all Heat exchangers, its optimal design is difficult. In this project, we have constructed a prototype to fulfill a specified performance. For enhancing heat transfer area, we have chosen four tube pass. However, experimental results have slightly deviated from theoretical results. Exact flowrate according to problem statement is difficult to produce, this is a reason of deviation of results. From HTRI software calculation, this this project is 2.3% oversized, this is also for responsible for deviation of results. However, the heat exchanger performed well to reduce hot water temperature. So, our objective of this project has been satisfied.

References

- 1.Heat and mass transfer – Yunus A. Çengel
- 2.Heat Transfer Equipment design – W. S. Janna

Acknowledgement

We heartfully thankful to the teachers and workers of MACHINE SHOP and WELDING SHOP of BUET for helping to developed this project.

